

THE CENTRALITY OF CONTEMPLATIVE PRAYER IN CELIBATE SOLITUDE AND INTIMATE RELATIONSHIPS

Sr. Anitha KONDAVETI JMJ

The author <anishowri@gmail.com> is from Andhra Pradesh, India, and belongs to the religious congregation of Jesus Mary Joseph (JMJ). She holds a Research Master's Degree in Theology from KU Leuven, Belgium, and is currently pursuing her doctoral studies at the same University. Her current research focuses on understanding the religious apostolate as a theological category of representation based on the Trinitarian theology and mission Christology of Hans Urs von Balthasar.

Abstract: The reciprocity between celibacy and contemplative prayer is clear, as the former nurtures contemplative immediacy to God, while the latter serves as a lifeline for a celibate life. The crises in apostolic religious life are often attributed to a lack of prayer, resulting from the demands of ministerial and professional responsibilities and interpersonal interactions. This article explores the role of contemplative prayer in the 'intimate' dimension of apostolic religious life, suggesting that contemplative prayer is the central support system that helps a celibate achieve intimacy with God and others.

Keywords: Celibacy, Intimacy, Contemplative Prayer, Authentic Solitude.

INTRODUCTION

Unlike other forms of consecrated life, the distinctive feature of the apostolic religious life is its foundational characteristic of merging a life of devotion (contemplative life, monastic tradition, mystical tradition, asceticism, prayer, etc.) with a life of work (ministry, charity, apostolate, service, etc.) in the world.¹ The adage encapsulating this combination

¹ Laetitia Aarnink and Louise V Laarhoven (eds.), *Sent by the Lord: The Spirituality of the Sisters of Jesus Mary Joseph* (Nijmegen: Titus Brandsma Instituut, 1997), 9.

is ‘contemplation in action’ or ‘prayer and work’ (*ora et labora*). In her analysis of the apostolic (ministerial) religious life following the Second Vatican Council, Sandra Schneiders emphasized that the contemplative and active (apostolic/mission/ministerial) dimensions of the apostolic religious life are nurtured by the embrace of consecrated celibacy. She says that “contemplative immediacy to God” and “social marginality” are the hallmarks of apostolic religious life, stemming from their voluntary commitment to consecrated celibacy, making it a prophetic life form within the Church.² It is important for us to understand the two concepts “contemplative immediacy to God” and “social marginality” as proposed by Schneiders.

Contemplative Immediacy to God: One enters celibate solitude by the voluntary choice of consecrated celibacy. The main goal of celibate solitude is nurturing contemplation, God’s nearness, and finally the experience of oneness with God.³

Social Marginality: By the voluntary choice of consecrated celibacy, the religious place themselves on the margins of society. Even though the ministry is carried out in the world, by giving up marriage, family, ownership of wealth, etc., the religious demote themselves from the dynamics of the present culture. This self-chosen social and cultural marginality enables them to stand up for those suffering in various ways.⁴

Thus, celibate solitude and contemplative prayer foster religious commitment to contemplation and action. The personal relationship with Jesus and desire for divine communion are nurtured, enabling the mission consciousness of the religious men and women to participate in the mission of the Church. This active participation in the mission of

² Sandra Marie Schneiders, *Finding the Treasure: Locating Catholic Religious Life in a New Ecclesial and Cultural Context*, Religious Life in a New Millennium 1 (New York: Paulist, 2000), 137.

³ Schneiders, *Finding the Treasure*, 138-139.

⁴ Schneiders, *Finding the Treasure*, 139-140.

the Church through the apostolic religious life makes celibate solitude a call for loving relationships, and not for withdrawal and isolation. Therefore, under the pretence of a celibate solitary lifestyle, interpersonal relationships and the aspect of intimacy should not be neglected, instead, they need to be fostered.

From Schneiders' presentation of celibate solitude, the reciprocity between celibacy and contemplative prayer is evident as the former nurtures contemplative immediacy to God while the latter is a lifeline of a celibate life. Nevertheless, as the crises in religious vocation, ministry, and relationships are often linked to a lack of prayer, it is important to focus on the reciprocity between interpersonal relationships and contemplative prayer, proposing that contemplative prayer is the central support system that helps a celibate achieve intimacy with God and others.

In this article, the first part briefly presents the relationship between celibacy and contemplative prayer, highlighting the need to focus on the relationship between contemplative prayer and interpersonal relationships in apostolic religious life. The second part focuses on understanding 'contemplative prayer as a central support system,' which balances celibacy and intimacy for an effective living of apostolic religious life. The paper proposes that contemplative prayer is a 'place' (a spiritual space) wherein divine and human relationships happen, are nurtured, and sustained so that a celibate can achieve intimacy with God and foster interpersonal relationships with fellow human beings.

1. CONTEMPLATIVE PRAYER AND CELIBACY

The apostolic exhortation *Vita Consecrata* presents Jesus' transfiguration as the basis of consecrated life, comprising both contemplative and active dimensions. Jesus' transfiguration consists of his contemplative immediacy to the Father and also reveals the mission of the Cross to

be fulfilled in his life.⁵ A Consecrated person whose life is modelled after Jesus' transfiguration is called to stand in the centre of the world as a living example of a transformed life.⁶ Communion and solitude, prayer and work, being with the Lord and going out in service are the dual facets of the single reality of consecrated life. Consecration implies mission, which can be theologically ordered by and in the mystery of the Trinity. The Trinitarian triad of love, goodness, and beauty, which indicates communion and mission, becomes the theological basis for the consecrated life.⁷ These Trinitarian characteristics of communion and mission point to the significance of the contemplative dimension of apostolic religious life in fostering the divine union and human relationships.

1.1 Celibate Solitude

'Celibate God-quest' is one of the important characteristics of apostolic religious life.⁸ Distinct from other religious traditions, in Christianity, the commitment to celibacy is not only about remaining unmarried, the practice of asceticism and service, but most importantly, it is about an absolute and lifelong personal relationship with the person of Jesus.⁹ This commitment to living a celibate life for God and desire for divine union, actualized in a personal relationship with Jesus, permeates every aspect of religious life. This single-minded quest for divine union is fostered in and through contemplative prayer.¹⁰ Contemplative prayer is not limited to

⁵ John Paul II, *Vita Consecrata*: Post Synodal Apostolic Exhortation on the Consecrated Life and its Mission in the Church and in the World, Rome, 1996, no.14.

⁶ Romanus Cessario, "Love, Friendship, and Beauty," *Logos* 11/4 (2008): 149.

⁷ Cessario, "Love, Friendship, and Beauty," 150.

⁸ Sandra Marie Schneiders, *Buying the Field: Catholic Religious Life in Mission to the World*, Religious Life in a New Millennium 3 (New York: Paulist Press, 2013), 96.

⁹ Sandra Marie Schneiders, *Selling All: Commitment, Consecrated Celibacy, and Community in Catholic Religious Life*, Religious Life in a New Millennium 2 (New York: Paulist, 2001), 142.

¹⁰ Schneiders, *Buying the Field*, 96.

the exercises of mindfulness, awareness, imaginative prayer, and other mental practices. Christian prayer is “essentially a relationship with a person who gradually becomes the affective centre and effective motivation of one’s life.”¹¹

The purpose of consecrated life, particularly the practice of asceticism, is a single-minded and whole-hearted return to God, for which commitment to consecrated celibacy is vital.¹² While the desire for divine union through contemplative prayer is common to all Christians, the commitment to consecrated celibacy makes it distinctive and particular to the religious life.¹³ Contemplative prayer is the lifeline for the life of consecrated celibacy. It is the channel of communication between the self and his/her divine spouse. This contemplative communication results in intimate union, leading to the transformation of oneself into the likeness of God, embodying his values, his purpose, and his project here in this world.¹⁴ Thus, the essence and primary commitment of all forms of consecrated life is the God-quest. Therefore, it is important that the apostolic religious men and women are not overridden by the ministerial (apostolate) concerns but are grounded in and nourished by the contemplative prayer.¹⁵

The mutual influence of consecrated celibacy and contemplative prayer leaves the religious with a divine mission consciousness. The *Abba* experience of Jesus is the reality of his mission consciousness. Similarly, the primary commitment through consecrated celibacy and the divine experience through contemplative prayer is the reality of the mission consciousness of religious men and women.¹⁶ In their commitment to consecrated celibacy, the religious make

¹¹ Ibid.

¹² John Binns, “Monasticism – Then and Now,” *Religions* 12/7 (2021): 510.

¹³ Schneiders, *Buying the Field*, 96.

¹⁴ Schneiders, *Selling All*, 197.

¹⁵ Ibid., 158-159.

¹⁶ Ibid., 158.

God's project, purpose, and interest their own. They sustain this commitment through continuous divine contemplation and a quest for God. Their service to humankind to establish the reign of God is due to their intimate divine experience and a tangible relationship with the person of Jesus.¹⁷

1.2 Relationality

Those in active apostolate are exposed to the concerns of the world due to their involvement in the active ministry with and for the people of God. This leads to unavoidable professional and personal interactions with others. Thus, an active religious person has fewer possibilities for contemplation and meditation of the divine as compared to a monastic.¹⁸ Due to the ministerial demands and personal contacts, engaging in contemplative prayer is often perceived as an arduous task. As a result, its influence on interpersonal relationships is easily dismissed, highlighting only the exclusive mutuality between celibate solitude and contemplative prayer. However, in the context of apostolic religious life, which is founded on the communion and mission dimensions of Christ's transfiguration, a celibate cannot avoid but rather develop interpersonal relationships by fostering a love that is deeply personal and universal in its scope.¹⁹ "Celibacy is not an alternative to intimacy but a different – often a more difficult – way of achieving intimacy. Anybody who is celibate must commit to developing a love that is deeply personal as well as universal in its scope."²⁰

¹⁷ Schneiders, *Buying the Field*, 95-98.

¹⁸ A monastic (male or female) is described as a Christian who leaves the world and all its concerns in response to a special call from God and commits oneself to conversion, asceticism, and prayer. Monastic life is a synonym for a life of prayer because the space created by the abandonment of all concerns of this world, through the practice of silence, asceticism, renunciation, repentance, etc., is occupied with prayer, meditation, and contemplation of the divine. <https://thevalueofsparrows.wordpress.com/2017/06/26/prayer-contemplative-prayer-an-introduction-by-thomas-merton/> (accessed on 20.05.2025).

¹⁹ Donal Dorr, "Celibacy," *Furrow* 55/3 (2004): 140-141.

²⁰ Dorr, "Celibacy," 141.

As solitude and a quiet time of prayer are necessary conditions for one to enter into a contemplative union with God, those involved in the active apostolate are challenged to be in union with God amid their ministerial responsibilities and personal interactions. By being attentive (consciousness) to the presence of God in everything, the apostolic religious can develop and cherish the contemplative presence of God, to bridge prayer and work, contemplation and action.²¹ Ignatius of Loyola instructed his newly founded order that his vision was not to maintain the balance between contemplation and action but to be the contemplatives in action. To find God in everything and everything in God. The ministry in all its variety must be contemplative of God's grace and presence.²² Contemplation of the love of God moves to action, and the action itself draws one into the contemplative presence of the divine.²³ As the apostolic religious life is not a withdrawal from the world but a journey into the world to live with and for the people, the commitment to celibacy must not make them cold, distant, closed-in workaholics, shrunken through burnout and meaninglessness. Instead, they need to develop genuine interpersonal relationships with a loving openness to others.²⁴

Chastity or celibacy cannot be well lived in isolation. Chastity is indeed a call for love and relationship. Therefore, interpersonal relationships and intimacy cannot be neglected or forcibly given up. Instead, these should be fostered to live a fruitful life of chastity/celibacy. How can this be done? What helps to foster interpersonal relationships and intimacy in the lives of those who voluntarily choose celibacy? In

²¹ Gerald M. Fagin, "Contemplation to Attain Love: A Paradigm for Apostolic Prayer," *Review for Religious* 60/2 (2001): 160.

²² Robert Bireley, *The Refashioning of Catholicism, 1450-1700: A Reassessment of the Counter Reformation* (Washington DC: Catholic University of America Press, 1999), 33.

²³ *Vita Consecrata*, no. 74.

²⁴ Dorr, "Celibacy," 142.

response to this question, we propose that contemplative prayer not only bridges communion and mission but also fosters the personal and universal love that a celibate is committed to developing in his/her life.²⁵ Thus, in the following sections, building on Dorr's suggestion that prayer is one of the support structures for effective celibate living, we will see how contemplative prayer becomes a 'place,' i.e., 'a spiritual space' where celibacy and intimacy are mutually nurtured.

2. CONTEMPLATIVE PRAYER AND INTIMACY / INTERPERSONAL RELATIONSHIPS

It is generally believed that a celibate (living a solitary life devoid of all worldly concerns) can easily enter into contemplative prayer, and in turn, one's commitment to celibacy is strengthened by this contemplative immediacy to God.²⁶ Because of this belief, a general perception is developed that intimate relationships and professional involvement (in this case, the apostolic/ministerial participation of the religious personnel) make it difficult for one to enter solitude and contemplative prayer. Hence, in this section, the focus is on understanding the centrality of contemplative prayer in the relational dimension of a celibate person. The relationality of an apostolic religious person can be perceived in two different ways: (1) Relationship as service, and (2) Relationship as friendship.

²⁵ Ibid., 143. Donal Dorr proposes that prayer and meditation act as a support structure to channelise one's celibate energy and creativity.

²⁶ To give an example, Thomas Merton, a great spiritual writer, monk, and contemplative, believed that to reach the deepest level of contemplation, one must completely give up the active life. However, despite his monastic vocation, Merton always felt connected to those outside the monastery, actively involved in social justice. He struggled to balance the instinct both for contemplation and action (as an active writer and monk), and finally, to balance the demands of contemplation and action, Merton tried to divide contemplation into different levels. Ross Labrie, "Contemplation and Action in Thomas Merton," *Christianity & Literature* 55/4 (2006): 475.

2.1 Relationship as Service

According to Thomas Merton, religious contemplation is a state of consciousness of God as he truly is and not as we perceive him based on our experiences, needs, anxieties, etc. In this way, contemplation is not a separate activity but becomes the basis of every human activity. In contemplative prayer, through the consciousness of God's true existence, we are enabled to reach the deepest levels of our being, and our perception is transformed in such a way that we begin to see ourselves as God sees us.²⁷ Thus, in contemplative awareness, the understanding of the self and its relationship to God is transformed, and this transformation is manifested in one's relationship with fellow human beings and the entire creation.²⁸

God is always present in every baptised soul and also in every part of creation. However, this awareness remains dormant until one brings it to consciousness through contemplation supported by a life of service and asceticism.²⁹ According to this explanation of religious contemplation, one aspect to be noticed is that contemplative solitude implies the presence of the 'other.' In contemplation, we are coming to consciousness of the reality of God's presence, and this not only opens us to the reality of our innermost being but also to that of the 'other' (not only humans but the entire creation).³⁰ Thus, in contemplative solitude, a religious is brought to the consciousness of the reality of fellow human beings in need of justice and charity, and this brings us to the actual challenge of balancing the contemplative union with God and engaging in action (service) with and for others.

In response to this challenge of balancing contemplation and action, Merton presented the concept of contemplation

²⁷ Thomas Merton, "The Inner Experience: Notes on Contemplation (I)," *Cistercian Studies* 18/3 (1983): 11-14.

²⁸ Labrie, "Contemplation and Action in Thomas Merton," 477.

²⁹ Thomas Merton, "The Inner Experience: Christian Contemplation (III)," *Cistercian Studies* 18/3 (1983): 206.

³⁰ Labrie, "Contemplation and Action in Thomas Merton," 477.

at three different levels: natural, infused, and active.³¹ Natural contemplation is explained as something similar to the contemplation or the imagination of an artist or a philosopher who contemplates the spiritual and ontological appearances of a being.³² Natural contemplation builds the relationship between God and creation as the created world is the locus of God's presence and action.³³ For Merton, infused contemplation is most valuable as it is the moment wherein the soul is flooded and saturated by the divine presence. It is a moment of consummation between the divine and the human soul. This gives us the idea that any active involvement disrupts this divine communion. However, Merton does not perceive contemplation and action as opposite to each other, but instead as complementary to each other, for action without contemplation is an empty task devoid of faith.³⁴ To explain this he presents the third type of contemplation as active contemplation, which is explained as the daily life experience of God flowing from an individual's spiritual vitality and creativity based on which a person draws his or her 'strength' not in receiving from 'things and people' but by giving oneself to 'life and others.'³⁵ Thus, it is evident that through contemplative prayer, one cannot but engage in action, because in active contemplation, one begins to see the society's reality not only as being part of it but through the mind of the One who shaped or created such society. For a religious (as it was for Merton), the vision of society is dominated by the personality and vision of Christ. Thus,

³¹ These three levels are presented in his essays, "Poetry and the Contemplative Life" (1947) and "Poetry and Contemplation: A Reappraisal" (1958).

³² Thomas Merton, "The True Legendary Sound: The Poetry and Criticism of Edwin Muir," *The Sewanee Review* 75/2 (1967): 318.

³³ Xiaoyan Xu, "Analogia Entis in a Monastic Vision: Thomas Merton's Answer to the Modern World," *Religions* 15/1 (2024): 72.

³⁴ Thomas Merton, *Contemplative Prayer* (New York: Herder and Herder, 1969), 143.

³⁵ Thomas Merton, "The Inner Experience: Kinds of Contemplation (IV)," *Cistercian Studies* 18/4 (1983): 291.

through religious (active) contemplation, one can participate in the vision of Christ for our society in history intersected by transcendental reality.³⁶

“The contemplative life is not and cannot be a mere withdrawal, a pure negation, a turning of one’s back on the world with its suffering, its crises, its confusions, and its errors.”³⁷ Merton’s writings on social issues prove to be the perfect example of what true solitude and contemplation must result in. The solitary and contemplative prayer eventually transforms into compassion. In such solitude and contemplation, one not only finds God but also God’s people who cannot be separated from God. And this is the deepest realization of love, which can only happen in contemplation.³⁸ According to Merton, everyone is not called to be a monk or religious, but everyone must find solitude and silence to foster contemplative prayer, because it is required for everyone, to become aware of one’s true and inner self, which will then open the way to the experience of God and openness to the reality of society.³⁹ Hence, true contemplative prayer implies a movement of self through and by God towards the other in self-giving service. This contemplative movement of self towards self-giving service to the other explains ‘relationship as service’ in the relationality of an apostolic religious person.

2.2 Relationship as Friendship

The foundational commandment of Christianity is to love God with all your being and your neighbour as yourself. Every form of Christian life, including the apostolic religious life, is centred on this command. Thus, a celibate person, through his/her contemplative immediacy to God, is enabled to go out in love and service to the neighbour.

³⁶ Labrie, “Contemplation and Action in Thomas Merton,” 482.

³⁷ Albert J. Raboteau, “Thomas Merton: Contemplation in a World of Action,” Chapter 5 in *American Prophets: Seven Religious Radicals and Their Struggle for Social and Political Justice* (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 2017), 121.

³⁸ Raboteau, “Thomas Merton: Contemplation in a World of Action,” 121-122.

³⁹ *Ibid.*, 129.

But, as human beings, our movement towards the other is not always limited to service and mission but also calls for friendship and a personal relationship.⁴⁰

Dom Bernardo says that the divine commandment of love in a celibate who is consecrated to God through the profession of evangelical counsels is manifested in three different forms, namely, mystical love, mission love, and community love. The mystical love is the relationship of the soul with its divine spouse (corresponding to the infused contemplation of Merton), and the mission love is expressed in the service and charity with which one moves out to those in need (corresponding to the active contemplation of Merton). These two forms of love are briefly dealt with in the previous sections, as we have seen the contemplative and mission dimensions of religious life expressed as the contemplative immediacy to God (mystical love) and the social marginality (mission love). The third type of love, the community love, is expressed as friendship and communal love (*koinonia*) for and with fellow human beings.⁴¹

In the lives of religious men and women who voluntarily choose celibacy, interpersonal relationships and the aspect of intimacy are often seen as problematic. There is a certain clamour and confusion implied in this aspect of relationality in the life of a celibate religious. Hence, the focus here is to understand the role of contemplative prayer in the fruitful living of the intimate dimension of relationality in the lives of celibate religious.

The virtue of chastity blossoms in friendship. It shows the disciple how to follow and imitate him who has chosen us as his friends, who has given himself totally to us and allows us to participate in his divine estate. Chastity is a promise of immortality.⁴²

⁴⁰ Bernardo Olivera, "Celibacy as Love Relationship," *Cistercian Studies Quarterly* 39/4 (2004): 421-423.

⁴¹ *Ibid.*, 421.

⁴² *Catechism of the Catholic Church*, no. 2347.

The Catholic Church explains that celibacy/chastity does not prevent one from relating to others, but orders one to form harmonious relationships of love after the example of the One who gave himself to us. “The harmony consists basically in accepting differences, respecting privacy, discerning distance and gestures, communicating person to person, and being totally present to the relationship.”⁴³

Personal interactions, ministerial responsibilities, relationships, and other aspects stemming from the apostolate and community life should not be regarded as distractions but rather viewed through the lens of charity. This perception makes chastity a self-gift which indeed leads one to the love of neighbour. Chastity must not be reduced to sexual relationships, but must be open to harmonious friendship, mission, and Christ’s witness.⁴⁴ What helps a celibate develop these harmonious interpersonal relationships, given the biological, human, and sensual need for intimacy? A regular and honest prayer of contemplation can help a celibate person order their passions, desires, and dreams into chaste relationships of love. How does contemplative prayer help transform these human relationships, often seen as distractions, into the immortality of chastity, enabling one to enter the divine union?

3. THE CENTRALITY OF CONTEMPLATIVE PRAYER – A ‘PLACE’⁴⁵ OF SUPPORT

“Praying is consciously paying attention to the central relationships of our lives, with ourselves, with others, and with God.”⁴⁶ Our relationship with God is the foundation

⁴³ Olivera, “Celibacy as Love Relationship,” 423.

⁴⁴ Ibid.

⁴⁵ The word ‘place’ does not mean a physical place but a spiritual space or a metaphysical space which is created by the Divine grace and the human desire for divine communion. The analogy of ‘place’ is used as it is appropriate to understand that the relationship between two individuals is happening concretely and not in abstract.

⁴⁶ Rick Malloy, “Prayer is a Risk,” *Review for Religious* 66/2 (2007): 172.

as well as a mirror image of our relationship with others.⁴⁷ Prayer is an act of love and requires a continuous, conscious, and disciplined effort to experience God.⁴⁸ Thus, prayer is relational and interpersonal. It is not a mere communication with some supernatural, abstract, invisible, and intangible object, but with a God who is personal (a person) and relatable. Based on this understanding of prayer as relational (interpersonal), we can say that contemplative prayer, understood not merely as a practice but as a way of life, becomes a vital space where the relational dimension of a person, both divine-human and human-human, is deepened. It nurtures an ongoing encounter that forms and sustains authentic relationships with God and others. God is ever waiting to draw us into the mystery of God, provided we are ready to begin the spiritual journey into the divine mystery. The contemplative prayer is a ‘place’ where one begins and goes through this journey.⁴⁹ In the following part we will further explore the understanding of contemplative prayer as a ‘place’ and its benefits in the intimacy dimension of a celibate.

3.1 Etymology

The etymological origin of the term contemplation⁵⁰ can be understood from both Greek and Latin. In Greek, *theoria* meant ‘contemplation,’ which denoted experiencing, observing, and grasping the knowledge of reality. In Latin, the word ‘contemplation’ is derived from the verb *contemplari*, which means ‘to observe or to gaze at.’ It is formed by combining *con*, meaning ‘with’ or ‘together,’ and *templum*, which refers to ‘an open space for observation,’ mostly associated with religious ceremonies. The understanding

⁴⁷ Ibid, 172.

⁴⁸ Ibid., 171.

⁴⁹ James Danaher, “Contemplative Prayer & the 21st Century,” *New Blackfriars* 93/1046 (2012): 454.

⁵⁰ In this article, the terms ‘contemplation’ and ‘contemplative prayer’ are used interchangeably. Both terms refer to the act of Christian contemplative prayer in general, particularly in the context of the apostolic religious life.

of ‘contemplation’ as ‘observing’ encompasses focused, thoughtful attention to something and being present to it.⁵¹ The etymological consideration of the term ‘contemplation’ makes it clear that the act of contemplative prayer, wherein we are conscious of the central relationships of our lives, can be perceived as a ‘place.’ A place where the concerned individuals in a relationship are focused on and present to each other, irrespective of their physical presence, but in contemplative awareness of the divine.

3.2 Solitude

To further understand this allegory of ‘contemplative prayer as a place,’ it is important to consider the concept of ‘solitude,’ a fundamental requirement for contemplation.⁵² To better understand contemplative prayer as a support structure for celibacy and intimacy, it is necessary to focus on the nature of solitude and its characteristics. While there are many theories of solitude based on different perspectives, like biological, developmental, and social, the focus here is on the cognitive theory of solitude, which is not limited to intellectual consideration of solitude but is derived from the meaningful experiences of solitude.⁵³

The cognitive theory of solitude focuses on the difference between authentic solitude and pseudo-solitude. The fundamental difference between the two lies in our choice to be solitary. “Authentic solitude is typically based on a decision to be alone; in contrast, pseudo-solitude, in which loneliness predominates, involves a sense of abandonment or unwanted isolation.”⁵⁴ Since humans have an innate social and relational nature, the choice of

⁵¹ <https://www.contemplation.info/etymology-of-contemplation> (accessed on 02.04.2025).

⁵² Keith R Maddock, “Contemplative Prayer (The Visions of Thomas Kelly and Thomas Merton),” *Quaker Religious Thought* 92/1 (1999): 46.

⁵³ James R. Averill and Louise Sundararajan, “Experiences of Solitude,” in *The Handbook of Solitude*, eds. Robert J. Coplan, Julie C. Bowker (Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley & Sons, 2013), 100.

⁵⁴ *Ibid.*, 91.

solitude is often misconstrued as leading to loneliness. However, this is not the case with authentic solitude, because it can help preserve the sense of community while being solitary.⁵⁵

James R. Averill and Louise Sundararajan have conducted an empirical study and developed the cognitive theory of solitude based on the experiences of solitude. This theory is developed within the cognitive space known as a designer environment.⁵⁶ These designer environments have a structure. The cognitive structure of solitude, developed based on the meaningful experiences of people, is divided into relational and non-relational dimensions. The relational dimension of solitude⁵⁷ is further divided into inner-directed (relationship with oneself) and outer-directed (relationship with others) relational dimensions. The inner-directed solitude results in enlightenment (creativity, self-discovery, and self-enrichment) and freedom (free from all concerns), while the outer-directed leads to communion (intimacy, community, spirituality).⁵⁸ Thus, when an apostolic religious commits oneself to celibate solitude, it is essential to be conscious of the relational and non-relational dimensions of solitude. As the choice of celibacy is a voluntary action, it implies a great self-responsibility, or else authentic solitude might result in pseudo-solitude dominated by loneliness, meaninglessness, and loss of purpose.⁵⁹

⁵⁵ *Ibid.*, 91-93.

⁵⁶ “Designer environments are the cognitive counterpart of niche construction by animals.” Averill and Sundararajan, “Experiences of Solitude,” 100. Unlike the natural habitats, these designer environments are found only in the cognitive space, and they include functions like thinking, reasoning, habit forming, training, skill development, etc. These designer environments help build up a cognitive theory/structure for various cognitive, emotional, and spiritual aspects like love, solitude, self-perception, resilience, etc., required for flourishing of one’s life.

⁵⁷ In considering the relational dimension, the focus is on the authentic solitude, because the non-relational dimension of solitude leads to loneliness and results in pseudo solitude. As this article tries to balance the intimacy and celibacy, the focus is on authentic solitude.

⁵⁸ Averill and Sundararajan, “Experiences of Solitude,” 101.

⁵⁹ *Ibid.*, 93.

3.3 Contemplative Prayer – A Support Structure

As seen in the etymology, contemplation is an ‘open place for observation.’ For anyone to enter this space of contemplative prayer, solitude is a prerequisite. By the voluntary choice of celibacy, the apostolic religious is enabled to experience solitude. In experiencing authentic solitude, the religious are present to their personal (inner-directed) and professional/ministerial (outer-directed) relationships. As said earlier, prayer is paying attention to the central relationships of one’s life, both human and divine.⁶⁰ And more importantly, a contemplative form of prayer is about being present to / observing these relationships. Accordingly, the contemplative prayer is possible only in an atmosphere of authentic solitude (relational) and not pseudo-solitude (non-relational). Thus, interpersonal relationships are not an obstacle to contemplative prayer, rather, they facilitate the contemplative prayer.

Contemplation and action are not two separate actions but one, as expressed by Ignatius of Loyola, that the apostolic religious are ‘contemplatives in action.’⁶¹ According to Thomas Merton, contemplative prayer is not a separate activity but a constant recognition/awareness of God as the core of our innermost being, grounding and leading us to love. Similarly, Thomas Kelly says that contemplative prayer leads to ‘love-infused perception’ of the world.⁶² “Contemplation involves entering into the core of our being and then passing through that core and out of ourselves into God and into God’s world with a renewed sense of vocation.”⁶³ The contemplative prayer is a place where this passing through of oneself into God and others takes place. Hence, the voluntary choice of celibacy/chastity enables one to experience authentic solitude, which in turn

⁶⁰ Malloy, “Prayer is a Risk,” 172.

⁶¹ Robert Bireley, *The Refashioning of Catholicism, 1450-1700*, 33.

⁶² Maddock, “Contemplative Prayer,” 44.

⁶³ *Ibid.*, 45.

leads to contemplative prayer in which one's interpersonal relationships are nurtured, strengthened, and transformed.

CONCLUSION

Contemplative prayer is a permanent space in the life of an apostolic religious person. In this space, the religious is constantly journeying from oneself through God to others. During this journey, the religious is present to oneself, to God, and others, transforming the interpersonal relationships into both service and friendship, in light of God's reality. Hence, on the one hand, reciprocity between celibacy and intimacy of a religious is required for one to experience authentic solitude and, in turn, nurture contemplative prayer. On the other hand, this reciprocity can only take place in the contemplative awareness of God in their daily life activities. Thus, celibate (authentic) solitude, interpersonal relationships (intimacy), and contemplative prayer are mutual and inseparable. They reciprocate with each other for a healthy and effective living of the apostolic religious life.

This paper focused on the mutual relationship between celibacy and intimacy in the life of an apostolic religious and how this mutuality is fostered in and by a permanent space called contemplative prayer. A religious who voluntarily chooses celibacy is personally challenged to create and sustain this space through the experience of authentic solitude. Thus, contemplative awareness of God in the core of one's being becomes a supportive structure (a permanent space in one's being) to help a celibate achieve intimacy both divine and human. Hence, the apostolic religious formation programmes need to focus not only on the reciprocity between celibacy and contemplative prayer but also on the reciprocity between intimacy and contemplative prayer.